

Full logo

Thumbnail

Colors

Font

Nunito Sans

'OSCU' in Nunito Sans Regular (283pt)

'Open Science Community Utrecht' in Nunito Sans ExtraBold (49.5 pt)

Use of the logo

New communities (i.e., established in 2020 or later) may adopt and customize our full logo for their own use¹. To ensure uniformity and prevent overlap of logos, you are **not allowed to alter** the following aspects of the logo (licensed under [CC-BY-ND](#), see note on BY below).

- 1) The shape and position of the symbol representing the 'O' (i.e., rotation is not allowed)
- 2) The color of the upper part of the symbol (#002060)
- 3) The font, size, and color of the letters 'SC'
- 4) The font and size of the final letter(s) that refer to a specific community
- 5) The font and color of the text underneath the logo. This text should be the full name of the community. Keep in mind that
 - a) the 'S' might stand for 'science' as well as 'scholarship';
 - b) in case of a national network of local OSCs the word 'community' in the text underneath the logo may be changed to 'communities'
- 6) The text underneath the logo should cover the full width of the logo

In practice, this means that new communities are allowed to

- 1) freely pick colors for the lower left part of the symbol (#ffc600 in the OSCU example) and the most right part of the symbol (#0070c0 in the OSCU example)
- 2) change the 'U' in OSCU to a letter representing the location of your community.
 - a) Only in case the name of the city of a local community consists of two words, two final letters may be used to refer to the location of the community (e.g., New Orleans).
 - b) In case a community is established for a whole country, or multiple local OSCs form a national network of OSCs, it is allowed to use two final letters that represent the country of this national community or national network of communities;
 - c) The two final letters selected to represent a (network within a) country need to be in agreement with the alpha-2 ISO 3166 list (see <https://www.iban.com/country-codes>).
- 3) change 'Utrecht' in the text underneath the logo to the location of your community
 - a) In case a community includes multiple institutions (e.g., multiple universities located in the same city), it is allowed to add one line of text

¹ Please reach out to Anita Eerland (anita.eerland@ru.nl) and/or Loek Brinkman (loek.brinkman@dans.knaw.nl) if you are thinking about establishing a new local OSC. They can provide you with a customizable template of the full logo and thumbnail. You can also contact Anita Eerland to add your logo to the overview of current OSCs, their logo and color codes.

containing the name of one of the institutes. This additional line of text should

- i) be in the same font (i.e, Nunito Sans ExtraBold) as the text containing the full name of the community (e.g., Open Science Community Utrecht);
- ii) cover the full width of the logo;
- iii) have the same color as the most right part of the symbol (#0070c0 in the OSCU example);
- iv) be used for internal communication only (e.g., in a local newsletter). For external communication the original logo without the added text containing the name of a local institution should always be used.

as long as:

- 1) the colors chosen for the two parts do not lead to a logo that is similar to that of another community. When in doubt, please contact that specific already existing community to discuss the issue.
 - a) Using the same colors as another community but in a different arrangement is allowed.
- 2) the colors chosen for the two parts are **not both red and/or orange**. Such an arrangement could lead to confusion with the logo of [Ubuntu](#). When in doubt, please contact Anita Eerland (anita.eerland@ru.nl) and/or Loek Brinkman (loek.brinkmand@dans.knaw.nl).
- 3) the color of the final letter(s) in the abbreviation (e.g., U in OSCU; NL in OSCNL) is the same as the color of the lower left part of the symbol.
- 4) the new logo is licensed under CC-ND, which states that others are not allowed to copy or modify your logo. This is to prevent others from creating logos based on *your* logo that do not adhere to these rules.

Note on CC-BY: You do not have to refer back to the OSCU logo every time you use your logo. However, it is required that you include the following statement at the bottom of the homepage of your website: “The logo of [your OSC] was adopted from the OSCU logo, originally created by Anita Eerland”].

Use of the thumbnail

New communities may adopt and customize the thumbnail of our logo for their own use. The following aspects are not to be altered (licenced under CC-ND):

- 1) the shape and position of the symbol (rotation is not allowed)
- 2) the color of the upper part of the symbol (#002060)
- 3) the font, color, and vertical position of the text within the symbol

Other restrictions:

- 1) The thumbnail may not be used without text in the symbol (to prevent confusion with the Ubuntu logo).
- 2) The colors of the symbol in the thumbnail should be congruent with the colors of the full logo if used by the same community
- 3) Text in the symbol should be congruent with the last word of the text underneath the full logo
 - a) In case a community is established for a whole country, or multiple local OSCs form a national network of OSCs, it is allowed to use the final two letters that represent the country of this national community or national network of communities (following the alpha-2 ISO 3166 list) as text in the symbol.
- 4) Your thumbnail should be licensed under CC-ND, which states that others are not allowed to copy or modify your thumbnail. This is to prevent others from creating logos based on *your* logo that do not adhere to these rules.

NB. Please note that the logos of OSC Galway, OSC Serbia, OSC Sweden, and OSC Turku deviate from the rules concerning the creation of the logo as explained in this Style Guide. These communities were established before the Style Guide was in place.

Overview of current OSCs and their logo and color codes

#002060

#0070c0

#cd7f32

#002060

#007a7d

#b30033

#002060

#8ec43f

#1daab2

#002060

#0070c0

#ebbd9

